

INTERNAL CONFLICT AS A RESULT OF BUILDING A POSSIBLE WORLD MODEL

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Abstract

The article shows the importance of temperature in the production of plastic pipes and how to eliminate possible temperature differences.

Keywords: temperature, lm35, digital, tubular, intermediate, thermocouple.

Polypropylene is a common copolymer raw material used in sanitary pipes due to its resistance to chemicals and heat transfer properties. The outer diameters, wall thickness, unit weights and tolerances of the manufactured pipes must comply with TS 10595. According to this standard, dimensions and tolerances in plastic pipes - polypropylene (PP) forms must be accurately measured.

As we know, pipes are randomly selected to measure the quality of pipes produced in the pipe industry

on a regular basis. As a result of research, it was decided to develop a prototype as follows. The concept of the system is shown in Figure 1. The heating process is carried out by a heating plate placed inside the sample box. The temperature is constantly monitored using a sensor in contact with the samples, and the heating-cooling intensity is regulated by an Arduino controller. I present to you an example with pipes inside to show the principal form of the device using the Planoplan editor program.

Fig.1. Design concept of temperature controlled test equipment.

The external device is a polystyrene box with dimensions of 250x250x250 mm and a wall thickness of 45 mm on each side. This box is designed to control the pipes produced in the field or in the factory. The box has a plastic lid (125x70x40mm) and two 50ml polypropylene tubes inside. The Arduino is supplied with 12V through the power input port. If an internal battery is used, the input voltage from an external source is determined using the output of the XL6019 converter.

The Arduino regulates the power supplied to the Peltier module / heater sensor by controlling the resistance of the digital potentiometer. The cables are selected according to the instructions in the sleemanj's MCP41 series library. The electronic schematic diagram of this device, which is designed to test pipes in different shapes, taking into account the Iso values, was developed in the frinzing program as follows.

Fig.2. The structure of the pipe temperature control device.

First, the pipe is given a high temperature and brought to the maximum. The values to be obtained during the next stage of solid cooling are displayed on the Lcd screen. Because the battery has self-protection circuits that shut off the output during overload, the system will not work if the cooling / heating system tries to draw a current greater than the maximum rated current. When using the battery, power consumption is limited to a safe level by the program. Note that this limitation is only related to the battery used here, and

batteries with a higher discharge rate are widely available.

As an alternative, it is possible to solve the problem using a 3-cell Li-ion battery with a nominal voltage of 11.1V in series, as well as eliminate the need for an amplified DC converter. Thus, the device will not have an energy problem. Since the results of the experiments correspond to the values, it is possible to build the circuit diagram of the device as follows and proceed to the next stage to prepare the device.

Fig.3. Electrical scheme of the developed device.

After the elements are prepared according to the scheme as hardware, the next step is to install a written control program on the microcontroller. The GPS module used here also helps us to determine the distance and area of the pipe with the help of several devices located in the field. The following algorithm was used to read the temperature range and the values of the GPS module:

```
float kp = 500.0; //; int ki = 5; int kd = 3.9;
float PID_p = 0.0; // int PID_i = 0; int PID_d = 0;
float Tmeasured = -1.0;
float Tsetpoint = 22.0; // Start around room temperature
```

```
float PID_error = 5;
float PID_value = 0;
```

At the present stage of development, the device, mainly the CPU cooler, is in preparation for size, moving parts and structural strength. However, after the refrigerator is replaced with a passive cooling system and a secondary packaging with a capacity of 95k Pa can be used, it can be used as a real device. One of the main

goals is to add other components to enhance the functionality of the device. During transport, the temperature profile can be stored in local memory for later verification or sent directly to the user via SMS using the GSM Arduino module on a regular basis.

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